

Impacts of groundwater flow on borehole heat exchangers: Lessons learned from Estonia

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ABSTRACT

The production of geothermal energy relies on subsurface properties. In low-enthalpy geothermal regimes, thermal energy extracted with a borehole heat exchanger (BHE) is the subsurface heat conducted from the rock and grout to the BHE fluid. Estonian geology provides a good opportunity to investigate how groundwater flow impacts BHE heat production. The hundreds of metres thick sedimentary rock sequence holds four main aquifers. We modelled single BHEs with lengths of 400 m, 500 m and 1000 m and a BHE field of ten 400-m wells at three sites across Estonia. Then, we parametrized different hydraulic conditions to compare how the groundwater flow velocity impacts the thermal energy yield of the systems.

Our results indicate that if groundwater flow increases above 0.03 m/day, it increases the total energy yield from 3 % to 20 %. Thermogeological parameters, such as subsurface temperature and thermal conductivity, affect the thermal energy yield of the wells more than the modelled groundwater flow. Our study provides an estimate of the thermal energy yield from different BHE types and the detailed sensitivity analysis. We conclude that geothermal energy is a significant renewable energy resource for Estonia and areas with similar geology and climate.

1. Introduction

With increasing demands for carbon-neutral energy sources and rising energy prices, geothermal energy is gaining interest not only in areas with high heat flow but also at unconventional sites with low heat flow densities and less favourable geological settings [1]. While traditional high-enthalpy systems are limited to areas with high heat flow, shallow low-enthalpy geothermal systems can be deployed for heating purposes practically anywhere in the world, with geothermal heat pump market having a 80 GW_{th} installed capacity and growth of 54 % between 2015 and 2020 [2]. Geothermal district heating and cooling is on demand in Europe with the total of nearly 400 systems and 14–17 new plants each year [1]; 45 large-scale shallow ground-source heat pump (GSHP) systems and seven medium-deep projects are in use or the developing phase in Finland [3] and two in Estonia. In very low subsurface temperatures, such as in the northern parts of Europe, the produced fluid temperature can be enhanced with heat pumps. Thermal energy extracted with a borehole heat exchanger (BHE) is the subsurface

heat conducted from the rock, groundwater, and grout to the BHE fluid. The system is optimized to replenish annually so that it functions sustainably, and subsurface fluids are not usually pumped in or out of the BHE system in the process.

The impact of groundwater on heat transfer in the vicinity of boreholes is often omitted in simplified BHE designs. This is usually a reasonable approach in crystalline rock settings or areas where rock is known to have low permeability. However, groundwater flow can influence the geothermal system, so it should be assessed in geology enclosing hydraulically conductive layers or in fractured rock [4–6]. The influence of groundwater on total heat flow in a well can be examined with the Peclet number, i.e., the ratio of advective to conductive heat transfer [5,7]. Furthermore, the groundwater impact can be assessed using *in situ* tests [8,9]. Groundwater flow increases the apparent thermal conductivity by up to 10–15 % [10,11].

Banks [12] provides a comprehensive discussion of the physical analogy of heat transportation and hydrogeology in a layered medium. Studies on the impact of groundwater flow on geothermal production

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have been conducted, for example, in China [13,14], Japan [15], Canada [4], the UK [16], Germany [17–19] and Sweden [10,20]. Although these studies have been conducted in various geological settings, and some have therefore considered layered geology and others fractured media, all cases have demonstrated how the impact of groundwater is concentrated in hydraulically conductive zones.

To date, the application of geothermal energy in Estonia has been very limited compared to the number of GSHP installed in the Nordic countries and geothermal research is correspondingly scarce [1]. To our knowledge, geothermal heat production potential in Estonia has not been published before. Hydrogeological monitoring in Estonia was established in 1946, and since then, both groundwater extraction and geological understanding of water-bearing layers have increased tremendously [21]. Typical GSHP applications are heating and domestic hot water production for single-family houses. Horizontal-loop near-surface geothermal systems mostly installed in Quaternary sediments prevail in Estonia due to their lower installation costs compared to vertical BHEs. The price of vertical BHEs mainly consists of the drilling cost, and the deeper the well, the heavier the drilling equipment that is needed. Based on estimates, approximately 100 open-loop installations and more than 2400 vertical closed-loop installations were operational or commissioned in Estonia by late 2021 [22]. The Geological Survey of Estonia is currently carrying out a research project to assess the geothermal energy production from 500 m BHEs. For this purpose, two small pilot plants for residential heating are in the building phase in Roosna-Alliku (central Estonia) and Tiskre, the western suburb of Tallinn.

In this paper, we focus on the effects of groundwater on geothermal energy production from a closed-loop BHE system in a low-enthalpy setting in Estonia. We compare four BHE types and demonstrate how their thermal energy yield depends on the groundwater flow velocity, among other parameters. Our study is the first of its kind in Estonian geology and contributes to the green energy transition of the country. Furthermore, the models and the results of sensitivity analysis are applicable in low-enthalpy geothermal settings around the world.

1.1. Geology and hydrogeology of Estonia

The subsurface geology of Estonia can be roughly divided into three major geological units: Quaternary loose sediments, Ediacaran and Lower Palaeozoic sedimentary rocks and Palaeoproterozoic crystalline rocks. The Quaternary sediments encompass a variety of glacial, glaciofluvial and glaciolacustrine deposits. The thicknesses of the Quaternary sediments remain less than 5 m in most of northern Estonia and over 10 m in southern Estonia, reaching over 200 m in the Haanja and Otepää heights. The sandy and clayey Quaternary deposits form relatively porous aquifers with mainly unconfined groundwater, which is directly influenced by meteorological conditions. The most important natural groundwater recharge areas are the Pandivere and Jõhvi uplands in northern Estonia and the Haanja, Otepää and Sakala uplands in southern Estonia.

The Lower Palaeozoic rocks are represented by Devonian sandstones (South Estonia), mostly carbonate (limestone and dolostone) rock sequences of Silurian–Ordovician age and Cambrian, mostly siliciclastic rocks [23]. The Cambrian rocks are predominantly siltstones with claystone interbeds. A distinctive Lower Cambrian claystone unit, the Lontova Formation, may reach up to 92 m in thickness in northern Estonia. The Lontova claystone is considered a regional aquitard with very low permeability (1×10^{-7} m/day).

The Silurian and Ordovician rock sequences are considered as one groundwater complex (carbonate rocks) but are divided into smaller units, aquifers and aquicludes with varying permeabilities, which are generally more hydraulically conductive in the topmost part [21]. Middle to upper Ordovician carbonate rocks are fissured and karstified and mostly form semi-permeable aquitards that have zones with better conductive properties.

The Cambrian rock complex is underlain by similar siliciclastic rocks of Late Proterozoic Ediacaran age [24]. The Voronka Formation sandstones and the coarse-grained siliciclastic rocks of the Gdov Formation form two major aquifers, the Gdov and Voronka aquifers, at 250 m depth in northern Estonia. The groundwater of the Gdov aquifer in NE Estonia contains high chloride concentrations (500–600 mg/L), so it is not useable as potable water, but due to elevated groundwater temperatures, it may have potential for geothermal energy applications [22].

The bedding of the sedimentary rocks is slightly southwards dipping at $0.10\text{--}0.25^\circ$ (about 2–4.5 m per km) (Fig. 1b) due to the general southward dipping of the peneplained Precambrian basement surface. The thickness of the sedimentary rock sequence is over 100 m in northern Estonia and more than 780 m in SW Estonia. The boundary between the Neoproterozoic sedimentary rocks and the Precambrian crystalline basement can be traced along the seabed of the Gulf of Finland, separating Estonia and Finland [22,25]. The topmost part of the crystalline basement is covered by weathering crust (mostly kaolinitic, with montmorillonite and illite clays), with thickness ranging from a few metres to several tens of metres. The Precambrian crystalline rocks are represented by a variety of gneisses and granites, which are similar to the Precambrian rocks of southern Finland and eastern Sweden [26]. The groundwater in the weathering crust and the crystalline basement is hydrodynamically connected with the lowermost sedimentary sequence of the Gdov aquifer. Groundwater is present in the weathered part of the crystalline basement, whereas the underlying crystalline basement rocks are considered to be impermeable [21].

The major petrophysical properties of the Ediacaran to Devonian sedimentary rocks (thermal conductivity, density and effective porosity) have previously been examined by Jõelet and Kukkonen [27] and Jõelet et al. [28]. Furthermore, Jõelet and Kukkonen [29] assessed the heat flow density in Estonia and discussed the influence of palaeoclimatic and hydrogeological effects on heat flow [30]. In northeastern Estonia, there is an elevated heat flow density anomaly [31]. The nature of the phenomenon is not fully understood, but it is likely to be a continuation of a larger heat flow density anomaly in the Saint Petersburg region.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Site descriptions

This study focused on three geothermal exploration boreholes drilled in Estonia in recent years. The locations of the drill sites are indicated on the simplified geological map of Estonia in Fig. 1a. The subsurface geology is represented by a thin layer of Quaternary sediments beneath the topsoil, followed by a complex of Lower Palaeozoic and Ediacaran sedimentary rocks that varies between 181 and 414 m in thickness (Fig. 2). A full list of thermogeological parameters for each stratigraphic layer is compiled in Appendix 1. The highest geothermal gradient values in NE Estonia can most probably be attributed to the higher heat generation in the crystalline basement rocks combined with the upward heat blanketing effect of the massive Lontova silty claystone formation. A distinctive feature observed in this study is the unexpectedly low groundwater temperatures measured in the sedimentary rock sequence of the Kolu-16 temporary well (Fig. 2), particularly in the interval from the groundwater level down to the base of the Upper Ordovician clayey carbonate rocks at about 220 m. The reason for such a low groundwater temperature remains unclear and warrants further temperature investigations in other wells in central Estonia.

2.2. Borehole and heat exchanger design options

We considered four different geothermal systems in our models: a single U-tube of 400 m, a 2×5 borehole field of U-tubes of 400 m, a 500-m-deep coaxial borehole, and a 1000-m-deep coaxial borehole (Table 1). The depths of energy wells were chosen based on the current widely

Fig. 1. a) Generalized geological map of Estonia with distinctive geological domains: the northernmost is Lower Cambrian to Lower Ordovician in olive green, followed by Middle Ordovician in the darkest shade of green. Next large domain in a lighter shade of green is Upper Ordovician with a small Middle Devonian (yellow) section in the east. Further south the layers are even lighter green: Llandovery and Wenlock, and the southernmost large domain is Middle Devonian in darker yellow and small section of Upper Devonian in light yellow. Jöhvi-1 is located in the Middle Devonian domain, near the eastern border of Estonia. Paldiski-1 is located in the Upper Ordovician domain, on the north-western coast. Kolu-16 is located in the middle of Llandovery domain. Across the map in N-S direction on the eastern side, there is a dashed line running from Letipea in the north to Valga in the south. The line marks the cross-section of Fig. 1b. b) Cross-section indicated on the map as a N-S dashed line. The section shows southwards dipping sedimentary layers on top of granitic bedrock. The layer is 600 m thick at the southern border of Estonia and approximately 200 m thick in the north, continuing as a thin layer under the Gulf of Finland.

available drilling rig capacity in Estonia and Finland. The 400- and 500-m-deep wells used a high-density polyethylene (HDPE) pipe as a heat collector and the 1000-m well had a vacuum-insulated tube (VIT) as a heat collector. The U-tubes were grouted with bentonite clay, and the coaxial collectors were cased so that collector fluid was not in direct contact with the surrounding rock. The collector fluid used in the 400- and 500-m wells was a commercial water-ethanol mixture with 28 wt% ethanol and a freezing point of $-17\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. For the 1000-m well, water was used as a collector fluid. These parameters are based on the good practices and available options in the geothermal industry of the Nordic countries.

2.3. Numerical model

We used the finite element modelling and simulation platform COMSOL Multiphysics® to construct the models for the BHEs. The model was based on similar COMSOL models described in Korhonen et al. and Piipponen et al. Our model comprised a 3D rock matrix and a single borehole or borehole field. Each geological layer was generated with 10-m accuracy.

Groundwater flow was described with Darcy's law:

$$\mathbf{u} = -\kappa/\mu \nabla p, \tag{1}$$

where κ is the hydraulic permeability of the rock matrix, μ is fluid

Fig. 2. Geological cross sections of the three boreholes, Paldiski, Kolu and Jöhvi and measured temperature curves in the boreholes. The grey shades around the borehole geological profiles indicate the same geological layers.

Table 1
Borehole technical parameters.

Pipe/parameter	400-m U-tube	500-m coaxial	1000-m coaxial
Borehole diameter (mm)	130	130	203
Collector material	HDPE	HDPE	VIT
Collector pipe diameter (mm)	55	75	76 (inner)/114 (outer)
Grout	Bentonite	–	–
Collector fluid	Water/ethanol	Water/ethanol	Water
	28 %	18 %	
Collector fluid flow rate (L/s)	0.5	0.5	3

viscosity and p is pressure. Groundwater flow was defined with the difference in the hydraulic head on opposite sides of the model dictated by the hydraulic gradient:

$$h = W_{model} \cdot \alpha, \tag{2}$$

where W_{model} is the length of the model and α is the gradient, with sensitivity tested using values ranging from 0 to 0.03. In the case of the gradient value 0, groundwater was not flowing.

The temperature field T was defined with

$$[(1 - \varphi)_s C_{p,s} + \varphi \rho_f C_{p,f}] \partial T / \partial t - [(1 - \varphi)_s + \varphi k_f] \nabla^2 T + \rho C_{p,f} \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla T = 0, \tag{3}$$

where t is time, φ is porosity, ρ is density, C_p is the specific heat capacity, k is thermal conductivity, \mathbf{u} is the fluid velocity vector, and subscripts s and f stand for solid and fluid, respectively.

Heat extraction was defined for the U-tube and coaxial collector separately as a set of partial differential equations on the outer boundary of the borehole, as in theoretical textbook for FEFLOW [32]:

$$\rho_f C_{p,f} \partial T / \partial t - k_f \nabla^2 T + \mathbf{u} \rho_f C_{p,f} \nabla T = f, \tag{4}$$

where f is a heat transfer coefficient defined through thermal resistance for both ends of the U-tube pipe and grout, and for the inner and outer tube of the coaxial collector. A detailed definition of the coefficients is listed in Diersch, [32].

The initial temperature was set by extrapolating from the measured temperature curves of each borehole. The boundary conditions applied to the model were the geothermal heat flux density at the bottom boundary of the model and the annual average initial temperature at the top boundary. Vertical boundaries were set as open boundaries far enough from the well, so the thermal effect of the wells did not reach them. Heat extraction was set as a monthly distribution visualized in Fig. 3, which corresponded to a heat transfer system lowering the

Fig. 3. Monthly distribution of the annual energy load.

entering water temperature by

$$\Delta T = E_{ann} \cdot N / (H/12) \cdot 1 / (\rho C_p Q), \tag{5}$$

where E_{ann} is the amount of heat annually extracted from the ground, N is the monthly fraction, $H/12$ is the number of hours in a month, ρC_p is the volumetric heat capacity of the working fluid and Q is its flow rate. The temperature of fluid leaving the heat pump was then imposed as a temperature boundary condition on the BHE inlet.

2.3.1. Model validation

Our model is validated by implementing the model parameters of Luo et al. [] and replicating their results with our COMSOL Multiphysics model. Luo et al. modelled a BHE field with 18 U-tube wells of 80 m, and they compare thermal output (specific heat rate) of the well and outlet temperatures of a homogeneous and layered subsurface model. The layered model uses geological and technical parameters of an existing well field in Nuremberg, Germany. Their results of modelled and measured scenarios show thermal output of 22.52–22.61 W/m and outlet temperatures of 7–7.5 °C during heating period and thermal output of - 17.99–18.14 W/m and outlet temperatures of approx. 15 °C during cooling period. The modelling work of Luo et al. was done with FEFLOW.

The outlet temperature results obtained with our model are in very good agreement with the results of Luo et al. (Fig. 4). The temperatures of the cooling period match almost exactly, and the temperatures of the heating period have % deviation. The specific heat rate obtained with our model is 21.42 W/m and -18.55 W/m for heating and cooling periods, respectively. This difference is most likely caused by the differences in model parameters that Luo et al. had not specified in their paper, but that are essential for our calculations, such as BHE fluid flow velocity.

2.3.2. Maximum annual thermal energy extraction

COMSOL Multiphysics was used to simulate 25 years of operation of the BHE systems. Parametrization of the model was performed with the Python MPH 1.2.3 library, a Java bridge by JPype. The model was set so that annually extracted energy E_{ann} was mapped against T_{min} , the minimum temperature of the borehole wall in the final year of the simulation. The limit for T_{min} was set so that the borehole outer boundary temperature would not drop below the freezing point of 0 °C and the injection temperature of the water–ethanol mixture would not drop below the temperature of -2 °C. The energy maximum was found by linear interpolation from three solved energy values.

In this study, the energy values were pure geothermal heat from the

Fig. 4. Comparison of outlet temperature curves in Luo et al. publication and our COMSOL model with their parameters.

subsurface, and additional energy from running the heat pumps was not assessed. Therefore, our results provide a first-order estimation of the amount of thermal energy from each location.

2.3.3. Sensitivity analysis

Our main goal was to test the sensitivity of the geothermal wells to groundwater flow, so models for each well depth at each of the three sites were run with a hydraulic gradient of 0, 0.001, 0.1 and 0.03, with a total of 48 model runs. Furthermore, the model was tested for sensitivity to a wide range of parameters. We tested geological parameters such as thermal conductivity, density, porosity and hydraulic conductivity at each site, the initial temperature of the rock column and the technical parameter of fluid circulation rate in the well. The analysis was run by varying each of the parameters individually by $\pm 10\%$ to examine the impact. The parameter variation was performed for an entire rock column, varying the geological parameters of each stratigraphic section, if applicable. Sensitivity analysis was again conducted for each well depth at each of the three sites and all hydraulic gradient values, totalling 576 model iterations. A full summary of the sensitivity analysis is provided in Table 2.

3. Results

3.1. Groundwater flow

Because the groundwater flow velocity varies with the hydraulic conductivity of each stratigraphic layer, sensitivity to groundwater flow is presented here for each set of results with a hydraulic gradient of 0 (no flow), 0.001, 0.01 and 0.03. The groundwater velocity values in the most conductive aquifer are from 0.006 m/d to 0.18 m/d (depending on the gradient) in Jöhvi, 0.003–0.09 m/d in Kolu and 0.005–0.15 m/d in Paldiski (Fig. 4). For example, in Jöhvi the flow velocity was 0,06 m/d when the gradient was 0,01 and 0,18 m/d with the gradient of 0,03 respectively.

3.2. Energy yield

The results are presented as the annual thermal energy yield (MWh/a) from each well and the average specific heat rate (W/m) for easier comparison of the well types. When the hydraulic gradient increases from 0 to 0.001, the influence of groundwater flow is under 1% (Fig. 5). The difference between the gradient of 0.01 (corresponding to Darcy velocities of max. 0.03–0.06 m/day) and the no-flow condition is 3–5% in shallow wells and 12–19% in well field cases. The differences in energy yield between the no flow condition and the highest groundwater flow (up to 0.09–0.18 m/day) are up to 10% in the case of a single U-tube (in Paldiski), 17% in the case of a single 500-m coaxial well (in Kolu) and 20–30% in all cases of the U-tube field. The deep coaxial well of 1000 m is less sensitive to an increase in groundwater flow, but the maximum increase in the thermal energy yield is still 3–6%.

The outlet fluid temperature of the wells varies with the monthly

Table 2
Sensitivity analysis parameters.

Parameter	Variables
Hydraulic gradient	0 (no flow) 0.001 0.01 0.03
Initial T	$\pm 10\%$ of each site-specific value
Rock thermal conductivity	$\pm 10\%$ of each site and stratigraphic layer-specific value
Rock density	$\pm 10\%$ of each site and stratigraphic layer-specific value
Rock porosity	$\pm 10\%$ of each site and stratigraphic layer-specific value
Hydraulic conductivity	$\pm 10\%$ of each site and stratigraphic layer-specific value
Well fluid circulation velocity	$\pm 10\%$ of each BHE type-specific value

Fig. 5. Groundwater velocity profiles of the three boreholes depending on the hydraulic gradients.

energy outtake distribution and decreases slightly over 25 years of extraction (Fig. 6). The lowest temperature values represent the end of the winter season, when the wells are exploited the most. These values are 0.8–3.1 °C in the U-tube well systems (both single and field) and 2.9–5.5 °C in coaxial (both 500 m and 1000 m) well systems (Table 3). The coaxial wells, in particular, display a very small temperature increase with an increase in the groundwater flow rate (0–10%), whereas in the U-tube well field, outlet temperatures are 1.5-fold higher or even doubled with an increase in groundwater flow. The highest outlet temperature values represent the summer season and are 10 ± 4 °C in all single-well systems and slightly lower, 4.4–8.6 °C, in the well field.

The increase in fluid flow has an impact on how the thermal plume around the well develops. In the case of no flow, the plume is symmetric (Fig. 8a), but enhanced groundwater flow brings warm water to one side of the well and spreads the cold plume in the flow direction (Fig. 8b).

3.3. Sensitivity analysis

Sensitivity analysis was performed on the subsurface temperature profile, rock parameters such as thermal conductivity, volumetric heat capacity, porosity and hydraulic conductivity, and collector fluid flow velocity by scaling each parameter separately by $\pm 10\%$. The most significant parameter is the initial temperature, with a change of up to $\pm 10\%$ compared to the initial energy yield value. The rock thermal conductivity and circulation fluid rate have the second largest impact, with

Fig. 6. Thermal energy yield and specific heat rate results with all modelled gradient values. The lines are for clarity and do not represent interpolation.

Fig. 7. Example temperature development of 400-m U-tube and 1000-m coaxial wells in Jöhvi over 25 years of exploitation.

Table 3

Outlet fluid temperatures of each well type after 25 years of utilization.

	Hydraulic gradient	U-tube 400 m		Coaxial 500 m		Coaxial 1000 m		U-tube 400 m field	
		T min	T max	T min	T max	T min	T max	T min	T max
Jöhvi	0	2.7	9.3	4.5	11.0	5.3	13.4	1.8	7.0
	0.03	3.1	9.9	4.8	11.4	5.5	13.6	2.5	8.6
Kolu	0	1.6	6.1	3.0	7.2	3.4	9.2	0.9	4.4
	0.03	2.0	6.6	3.0	7.6	3.6	9.6	1.6	5.7
Paldiski	0	1.8	7.3	2.9	8.2	3.5	9.9	0.8	4.8
	0.03	2.3	7.8	3.3	8.6	3.6	10.0	1.7	6.5

a change of roughly $\pm 3\text{--}8\%$. Sensitivity to changes in density, porosity and hydraulic conductivity are one magnitude smaller, with a change of $\pm 0.3\text{--}0.8\%$ relative to the initial case. Further patterns observed from the results are as follows: 1. The changes in the results are similar in the cases of a single U-tube and a U-tube field, the latter showing an amplified effect due to presence of ten wells. 2. The sensitivity of the 1000-m coaxial well displays little variation with respect to the location. The sensitivity to thermal conductivity is higher and sensitivity to the fluid circulation rate is lower than in the shallower wells. 3. Parameter

sensitivity is independent of groundwater flow in the case of the initial temperature, porosity and fluid circulation rate, and dependence is observed in the cases of hydraulic conductivity, rock thermal conductivity and density. With an increase in groundwater flow, the sensitivity of the hydraulic gradient and rock density increases, and the sensitivity to thermal conductivity decreases. The results of sensitivity analysis are presented in full in Appendix 2 in a similar manner to the sensitivity to the initial temperature in Fig. 9.

Fig. 8. Two figures with temperature field around the borehole and contours to delineate the change in the temperature around the borehole. In Fig. a the contour plot is symmetric because there is no groundwater flow. In Fig. b the contour plot is skewed due to the groundwater flow. In the permeable layers, on the right-hand side of the borehole where groundwater is flowing towards the borehole, contour lines are very close to the borehole, whereas on the left-hand side, where groundwater is flowing away from the borehole, the contour lines extend further away from the borehole. In the less permeable sections, the contours are nearly symmetric on both sides.

Fig. 9. Example of sensitivity calculations: sensitivity of varying the initial temperature by $\pm 10\%$.

4. Discussion

4.1. Assessment of groundwater impact

An increase in groundwater velocity increases the thermal energy yield in all cases, but the change is generally only visible when the gradient increases to 0.01–0.03 and groundwater velocities exceed 0.01 m/day. The groundwater flow velocity of 0.005–0.01 m/day had very little effect on energy yield. We can conclude that a low groundwater flow velocity of under 0.01 m/day has an impact on the energy production of geothermal wells so minor it can be omitted in the modelling. However, if groundwater flow is naturally or artificially increased near

the planned geothermal system, groundwater movements should be taken into consideration. Multiple studies agree with our finding that the Darcy velocity of approximately 1×10^{-7} m/s or 0.01 m/day is the threshold for a significant groundwater flow velocity [5,16,33,34]. In cases with a flow slower than this, outlet temperatures or the energy yield of the well are very close to the no-flow cases. This is in agreement with our results: under Darcy velocities of 0.01 m/day, the groundwater impact is $<1\%$. Banks [8] reported that a Darcy flux of 0.01 m/day results in at least a 20% reduction in the predicted temperature change in the heat carrier fluid, and a Darcy flux of 0.05 m/day a reduction of at least 41%. Comparing a no-flow condition with increasing the Darcy flow to 7×10^{-8} m/s or 2.9×10^{-7} , Abesser et al. [16] reported a 15.8%

and 22 % increase in energy yield, respectively, in the two study cases. Angelotti et al. [35] reported a heat rate change from -1% to $+105\%$ with Darcy velocities from 1×10^{-7} to 1×10^{-5} m/s in heating mode in Italy. On the other side, Rivera [36], reported that even negligible groundwater has a small impact on a BHE longevity.

In Paldiski, there is known groundwater extraction [37], so it is possible that the groundwater flow velocity is higher than under natural conditions, and thermal heat production could therefore potentially be at the higher end of the results set. The significance of groundwater flow is emphasized as the number of wells increases, as seen when comparing the energy yields of the single U-tube and U-tube field. Because high groundwater flow increases advective heat transfer, and the hydraulic gradient can be increased artificially with pumping, identifying areas with high permeability is a key to finding a higher geothermal potential. Therefore, geothermal energy extraction benefits from groundwater extraction, and areas with existing operations could be a good starting point for constructing geothermal systems. Regional groundwater studies must be conducted to assess the potential in detail.

4.2. Assessment of different well types and outlet temperatures

From the results, we see that all shallow wells yield around 10 ± 4 W/m and deeper coaxial wells 23–37 W/m, depending on the location. The reason for such a large difference is the choice of engineering parameters for the model: whereas all shallow wells were modelled with a fluid flow rate of 0.5 L/s, deeper wells were modelled with a fluid flow rate of 3 L/s. The latter is a more suitable rate, although still rather low compared to similar wells in Finland, which use up to 15 L/s (R. Niemi, personal communication, September 28, 2023). The deep coaxial well also had a well-insulated VIT pipe to prevent heat losses, unlike the shallow wells with HDPE pipes [38]. A field of ten U-tube pipes yields 20–30 % more than a 1000-m-deep coaxial well with little or no groundwater flow and up to 40–70 % with the increased hydraulic gradient. Therefore, considering that drilling technologies to depths of 400 m are already well established, the sole reason to favour the deeper wells is property space limitations in a densely built environment.

The U-tube field, in particular, yields rather low outlet temperatures, and its high thermal energy yield is due to the total number of boreholes. The field system is the most sensitive to the addition of groundwater flow. Coaxial wells, both 500 m and 1000 m, yield higher minimum temperatures than U-tube well systems and are clearly less sensitive to the added groundwater flow. The higher outlet temperatures of coaxial wells are associated with their depth. The 1000-m coaxial well produces similar outlet temperatures to the 500-m well, because its collector fluid flow rate is 6 times higher. As expected with the Estonian climate and subsurface temperatures, outlet temperatures are rather low and must be enhanced with heat pumps.

Geothermal energy systems sometimes face critique regarding the depletion of well heat, and that the well cannot therefore be claimed to be renewable. Geothermal heat does, indeed, need regulation to be used in a sustainable manner for the system to be truly renewable. Heat is brought to the system by conduction in the rocks and advection with the groundwater, and if the well is exploited faster than these heat transfer mechanisms bring more heat, the well faces a risk of freezing. From Fig. 6, we conclude that the well temperature decreases and increases symmetrically and there is very little or no decrease in the average temperature after 8 years, which means that the well replenishes sufficiently. The deep coaxial wells display some decline in temperature, but the well temperatures still reach equilibrium at 25 years, meaning that the wells can be claimed to be truly renewable.

4.3. Assessment of different locations

Thermogeologically, the largest differences between the three sites are related to the variation in the initial subsurface temperature and the depth of the hydraulically conductive layers. Jõhvi's superiority in terms

of thermal energy yield is associated with the initial temperature being around 28 % higher than in Kolu and Paldiski. The subsurface temperature is mainly related to the thermal anomaly in the area, but the blanketing effect of the thick Lontova claystone formation also plays a role. While the blanketing effect increases the temperature gradient, due to the low thermal conductivity of claystone compared to crystalline rock, geothermal wells should extend below the claystone formation to benefit from higher temperatures. Martinkauppi & Piipponen [39] reported a similar thermal blanketing effect of the Muhos claystone formation in northern Ostrobothnia, Finland".

The results for Kolu and Paldiski are close to each other, despite their differences in geology. Kolu has the lowest subsurface temperature down to 360 m and thermal energy yield in nearly all cases, with one exception: with a hydraulic gradient of 0–0.001, the thermal yield of a U-tube field is lowest in Paldiski. Hydraulically conductive sandstone beds occur at depths of 267–423 m in Kolu, whereas in Paldiski, the weathering crust above the crystalline basement rocks already starts at 230 m (Fig. 2). This can be seen in Fig. 5, with a different slope: with increasing groundwater velocity, energy extraction increases slightly more in Kolu than in Paldiski. This explains why extraction curves cross in the case of the U-tube field in Fig. 5.

In the case of the deep coaxial well, an increase in the hydraulic gradient results in minor changes. Most of the well is in impermeable crystalline rock, and heat extraction therefore relies on conductive transfer. The thinner the sedimentary layer there is on site, the less hydraulic properties affect the yield, given that the crystalline basement does not have water-conducting fractures.

Bridger and Allen [4] and Luo et al. [18] investigated the effect of layering on aquifer thermal energy storage and concluded that it has little impact on the final result, but, as in our study, their results demonstrated how permeable structures control heat and mass transfer. Gehlin and Hellström [10] presented a similar effect in a 2D model. In our results, this is visualized as the skewing of the thermal plume in Fig. 7.

Considering the very low production temperatures of our study, our findings can be widely applied to low-enthalpy geothermal systems in the other sedimentary basins, with relatively thick but weakly-cemented siliciclastic rock sequences, particularly in permeable sandstone units. The subsurface geology similar to Estonian extends southwards throughout the entire Paleobaltic basin to Latvia, Lithuania as well as to parts of Sweden, Belorussia and Poland [40]. Furthermore, Paleozoic sedimentary rock sequences occur in the Cambro–Ordovician sedimentary basins in eastern Canada [41] as well in the Paleozoic formations in Central Alberta Basin [42].

On a broader scale, our study method is not limited to the similar geological settings as in Estonia, but by modifying the model input parameters it is easy to apply to any kind of layered subsurface with or without fluid flow. Whereas our result is that at high groundwater flow velocities it has an impact on BHE thermal yield, with the knowledge of the subsurface properties, our method provides an estimate of expected production temperatures and thermal energy anywhere. It is therefore an essential tool in making geothermal systems sustainable for years ahead.

4.4. Sensitivity analysis assessment

According to both the site comparison and the sensitivity analysis results, the initial temperature has the most significant effect on the production yield: the effect of a 10 % change in rock density, porosity or hydraulic conductivity is practically insignificant. In the deep coaxial wells, a larger share of heat transfer occurs in the impermeable crystalline rock as conductive heat transfer. Therefore, the energy yield of deep wells is more dependent on the thermal conductivity and less on the hydraulic conductivity of the rock than in shallow wells. Engineering parameters other than fluid flow rate were not considered (e.g., borehole or collector dimensions or materials). Especially in the shallow wells,

however, the production yield is dependent on the fluid flow rate, and there are also dependencies on other parameters [38].

Our results align with those of Dehkordi and Schincariol [43], in that the most influential parameters are the initial and injection temperature, thermal conductivity and a Darcy velocity of 1×10^{-7} m/s or higher. In their study, variation in porosity had a larger impact on outlet temperatures than in our results, which is due to the larger difference in the tested porosity values.

4.5. Study limitations and further actions

There are limited thermogeological measurements from the deep Estonian subsurface, especially regarding local hydrogeology. Hydraulic gradient of the confined aquifers may vary across the stratigraphy, but in the lack of the detailed knowledge, the gradient was assumed uniform. Therefore, to be able to develop more detailed and accurate models, further field measurement data are crucial. Further actions involve including the abovementioned data in more detailed models. Another important area for future research is the sensitivity of the different borehole array to the groundwater flow rate. We did not examine whether there is a deviation in the results in case of the shape or the orientation of the 2×5 well field. Moreover, the current model yields a conservative estimate of the monthly distributed energy yield, not attaining the heat transfer system coefficient of performance (COP). The end-user energy consumption profiles differ and can be deployed in further modelling.

5. Conclusions

In the emerging market, it is essential to know whether drilling deeper is worth the investment. Here, we offer indicative thermal energy values for different BHE types and demonstrate that a 400-m-deep U-tube has a 6–12 % higher heat extraction rate than a 500-m-deep coaxial well. According to our modelling results, the parameters most significant to the BHE yield are the initial subsurface temperature and the thermal conductivity of the rock, as 10 % shift in these parameters can affect the energy yield of the system by 10 % and 6 %, respectively. For a single BHE, these parameters can be more significant than an impact of groundwater flow with hydraulic gradient of 0.01, which increases thermal yield from 2 to 8% depending on the location and well type. However, aquifers with a high groundwater flow velocity increase the geothermal potential in the researched area, and especially BHE fields with U-tube are susceptible to up to 30 % addition in thermal energy yield. A deeper coaxial well of 1000 m performs as well as a field of ten 400-m wells, so the decision regarding the geothermal system is dictated by the land area and installation costs.

With the rising interest in utilizing ground energy for local and

district heating and cooling, leveraging modelling-based knowledge can significantly accelerate advancements in the geothermal sector in Estonia. Our pioneering study has the potential to serve as a crucial reference point for energy system designs in Estonia and in areas with thick sedimentary basins around the world, for both decision makers and engineers. Additionally, the forthcoming direct measurements of site-specific thermogeological and hydrogeological parameters, following the deployment of the initial 500-m systems, will provide valuable practical insights for the burgeoning geothermal sector in the near future.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

K. Piipponen: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **A. Soesoo:** Writing – original draft, Resources. **T. Arola:** Writing – original draft. **H. Bauert:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Resources. **S. Tarros:** Writing – original draft, Resources.

Data availability

All data is available from the corresponding author upon request.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Kaiu Piipponen reports financial support was provided by Geological survey of Estonia. Teppo Arola reports was provided by Geological survey of Estonia. Alvar Soesoo reports financial support was provided by Geological survey of Estonia. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix 1. Geological parameters

JÖHVI-1 drill core							
Age & lithostratigraphy	Unit thickness [m]	Rock type	Thermal conductivity [W/(m*K)]	Density [kg/m ³]	Heat capacity [J/(kg*K)]	Effective porosity [%]	Hydraulic conductivity [m/d]
Quaternary sediments	9	Till & loam	1,7	2240	1000	15	1
Ordovician	Väo-Kallavere fms.	Limestone & dolostone	2,85	2560	1210	4	2
Cambrian	Tiskre fm.	Sandstone	3,05	2450	1470	23	3
	Lükati fm.	Claystone & siltstone	2,95	2200	880	22	1,00E-05
Ediacaran	Lontova fm.	Claystone	1,7	2240	880	10	1,00E-07
	Voronka fm.	Siltstone & sandstone	2,52	2240	1175	27	6
	Kotlin fm.	Claystone	1,7	2240	880	15	1,00E-07

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(continued)

JOHVI-1 drill core								
Age & lithostratigraphy	Unit thickness [m]	Rock type	Thermal conductivity [W/(m*K)]	Density [kg/m ³]	Heat capacity [J/(kg*K)]	Effective porosity [%]	Hydraulic conductivity [m/d]	
	Gdov fm.	50	Siltstone & sandstone	2,52	2240	1175	20	6
Proterozoic	Weathering crust	14	Gneiss	2,5	2200	1000	5	0,5
	Bedrock	401	Gneiss	3,5	3019	1000	1	1,00E-07
KOLU-16 drill core								
	Quaternary sediments	9	till, varved clay, silt	1,7	2240	1000	12	0,5
Silurian – Ordovician	Raikküla – Toila fms.	258	Limestone & dolostone	3,4	2530	1210	2	0,8
Cambrian	Kallavere – Vaki fms.	55	Sandstone & siltstone	2,71	2210	1175	27	2
	Lontova fm.	38	Claystone & siltstone	1,77	2360	880	10	1,00E-06
Ediacaran	Voronka – Gdov fms.	63	Siltstone & sandstone	2,17	2370	1175	20	6
Proterozoic	Weathering crust	9	Gneiss	2,5	2300	1000	5	0,5
	Bedrock	62	Gneiss	2,8	2670	1000	1	1,00E-07
PALDISKI-1 drill core								
Ordovician	Viivikonna – Varangu fms.	26	Limestone & dolostone	2,52	2460	1210	5	3
Cambrian	Tiskre and Lükati fms.	47	Siltstone & sandstone	2,37	2220	1175	24	5
	Lontova fm.	21	Claystone	1,55	2330	880	10	1,00E-07
Ediacaran	Kroodi fm.	87	Siltstone	1,7	2340	1175	27	5
Proterozoic	Weathering crust	1	Gneiss	3,2	533	1000	5	0,5
	Bedrock	577	Gneiss	3,5	3000	1000	1	1,00E-07

Appendix 2. Sensitivity analysis result graphs

T initial

Thermal conductivity

Density

Hydraulic conductivity

Porosity

Fluid flow rate

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